

FOREIGN LANGUAGES BASED ON MODERN METHODS ACTUAL PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF TEACHING

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Abstract: *This is in the article last in years' education in the field done increased reforms, foreign languages to teach with depends social necessity, official and informal language learning centers activity analysis will be done. And the beginning is beautiful class to his students English language in teaching face coming some problems and this problems eliminate reach methods is dedicated .*

Key words: *reading technique, writing technique, professional competence, decoding, encoding, graphic phonetics, phonetic criterion, traditional criterion, hieroglyph.*

Sign in . Usually, the teacher chooses the method of teaching and teaching a foreign language. The content of the teaching does not change much, but the way it is delivered to the students may change. There are several methods of teaching. The following teaching methods can be used during the lesson.

For example :

Lecture.

Give an example.

Demonstration.

Debate.

Questions and answers.

These methods are a method or form of communicating with students as well as elucidating the ideas that are aimed at the set goal.

A teacher should be able to choose the appropriate method for a particular situation or lesson. To choose a suitable and effective method of teaching , it is necessary to consider several factors.

Number of students. A specific situation. Suitability of the method to the intended purpose. If a text is discussed, it is appropriate to divide the students into small groups and have a team discussion. In this method, a technical tool - audio recordings - can be used. Time must always be taken into account when using methods.

It is known that in the 19th century many innovations were introduced to the methodology of learning a foreign language. Including the famous American Methodist R. Lado and linguist Ch. The audiolingual method created by Frize left a deep mark in history. Famous psychologist MD Berlitz says: "Learning a foreign language means learning to think in that language." It is known that language is an incomparable factor, an invaluable tool for people to know each other well, respect each other, and make friends. There are terms such as "reading techniques" and "writing techniques" in the written sources devoted to the methodology of language teaching. Reading technique - letter, the relation of letter combination with sound, and writing technique means the rules of writing a letter.

When teaching 2nd graders to read, they are first introduced to the English alphabet. In the process of introducing students to the English alphabet, it is appropriate to introduce their names and sounds separately. Because unlike other languages, English has 44 sounds, and some English letters represent more than one sound. Some words are pronounced differently than written, and this can cause some difficulties for students.

When teaching letters to an acquaintance, the sound is separated from the word, pronounced aloud, "sound articulation" is shown. Also, introducing the alphabet through **ABC** songs, in addition, giving their names under the pictures recommended for each sound - letters, will be the basis for the students' solid acquisition of new knowledge. Showing pictures of objects familiar to students in addition to letters helps to ensure their orthographic literacy, develop correct reading and writing skills, and also increase vocabulary - vocabulary.

In the 2nd grade, teaching to read and write in English is carried out in harmony. At the first stage of learning to read and write in English, the teacher faces the important task of developing an understanding of words, English letters and sounds, basic spelling rules in English, as well as increasing speech, thinking and vocabulary. Despite the fact that the letters of the alphabet are similar, the sound structure of the English language is fundamentally different from the sound structure of the Uzbek language. This creates difficulties for a child learning a foreign language.

For example, the reading of the letter **Aa [ei]** in English with four different sounds (**name -[ei], cat - [æ], park-[a], care-[e ə]**) sometimes causes a reading problem in a young school-aged child learning a foreign language. because in Uzbek this letter **Aa** is pronounced with only one sound (bayram, aka, lola). The solution of these and similar problems of lexicon, morphology, orthography related to reading and writing requires

the teacher to be competent in the correct use of his subject, general professional and modern pedagogical technologies in practice. Today, the following factors influence the development of the professional competence (abilities) of a teacher teaching a foreign language in primary classes: knowledge, life experience and continuous professional development.

There are specific requirements for teaching reading in English, which the teacher should take into account when developing his competence. To this the following includes:

- English of the language sounds, letters and their in writing of expression to himself special directions attention get
- of the student sound, letter, syllable, word and talk mutually relevance, harmony, integrity right perception to reach to teach
- orthographic literacy in development of sounds right pronunciation to be done, child's speech development and to growth positive effect show

Students English the alphabet learning with one in line, letters in the presence of short and simple syllable, words study exercise they do Reading to teach different method, technique and ways is available and they are:

1. Pictures and their names written cards using study to teach for example: a picture showing, from the student's picture name is asked and indicator finger using the letters one by one from the left ten directing is read.

2. Reading to teach initial stage decoding (**decoding**- code open reading) and encoding (**encoding** - encoding) methods use to the goal is appropriate. Because this method of student's study to learn one so much makes it easier. Decoding this is meaningless words through study to teach and encoding - meaningful words through study to teach means. Decoding method using initially letter compounds and simple the words study exercise will be done. A student in this and of the teacher attention of words meaning not only study to learn is directed. For example: **be, ce, de, fe, ge, he, je, ke, le, me, ne, pe, qe, re, se, te, ve, we, ze. bat, cat, dat, fat, gat, hat, jat, kat, lat, mat, pat, rat, sat, tat, vat, wat, zat.**

Only that's it remembers catch you need to decode it only to study to teach first stage is effective.

Encoding method using while students meaning meaning the words study with together, their translation with too they get to know each other. This method helps students to learn to read and increase their vocabulary.

For example: **bat, cat, fat, hat, mat, rat.**

be, he, me, she, we and etc.

This of methods study to teach in the process different efficient study techniques and methods with together use can

3. An analyst Analytical phonics - letters in the word sound expression through reading **for example:** a consonant in column 1 letters, in the 2nd column known one letter compound is given The students in this consonant the letters different letter compounds with study exercise they do and skill harvest they do

4. Graphic phonetics (Grapho **phonic**)- in the word the letters in the alphabet name with study technique. For example: **stain**. This technique is for student's letter names and of words writing order remembering to stay help gives

In a foreign language the writing in learning being studied language means (graphemes and written in the form of lexicon and grammatical units' application, that is to write technique) and written in the form thought statement reach is understood. The writing is grammatical and spelling to the rules compliance did without, written the idea statement is to reach Writing technique means, graphics (sound-letter relationship and of the letter meaning notice function), orthography (spelling). is caught. Spelling word and sentences writing, and to them circle the rules is the sum. He is productive speech activity considered information writing through from coding consists of To school step put each one the pupil he or this of the letter shape understand and write, small and capital letters ratio , pen to catch and right sit down the rules knows In students writing qualifications harvest to do for attention, intuition, perception achievement , memory like psychophysiological functions participation is enough This connections in the brain is strengthened and preserved remains .

Spelling in 2nd grade in teaching teacher in linguistics is available known criteria to know necessary

1. Phonetic criterion: word writing it represents to the sound suitable will come for example: **pen, ten, not, hot**.

2. Traditional criterion: phonetic and morphological spelling according to the rule does **not** obey historically acceptance done way keeps writing. For example: **door, one**.

3. Hieroglyph (ideography) criterion: pronunciation the same spelling different (homonymous) words. For example: **here-hear, right-write**.

Writing complicated psychophysiological activity being, then speech analyzers all of them participation is enough Written speech sentences right make up and the words right to write known requirements being placed with is characterized. Baby words how

heard if so, so not to be written know them right pronunciation to do and to write to learn necessary Written speech take over based on in children different texts about data surface will come This period written speech just now form started so, in the child himself wrote thoughts, words and the letters control reach qualification yet not developed will be Teacher's main task this qualification is to develop.

Summary in place that's it to emphasize must be English in the language student's speech qualifications in teaching from the teacher wide comprehensive knowledge, skill and creativity demand is enough with that together, modern English teacher always, continuously own on performance, innovative pedagogical technology and information communicative from technologies efficient use it is necessary

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